

BERDAK — AS THE FOUNDER OF KARAKALPAK LITERATURE

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Annotation: This article provides information about Berdaq's prominent region in Uzbek and Karakalpak literature, highlighting his life and innovative work. The article emphasizes the enormous significance of Berdaq's literary achievements, which embody people songs, a number of legends, proverbs and sayings, epic narratives, and epic poems, as nicely as his perception for the poems of well-known poets.

Keywords: Writer, proficient poet, Karakalpak people singer, thinker, truth, freedom, humanism, nationalism, courage, independence, the poet's loss of life.

Berdak is a outstanding parent who is popular all through Uzbekistan and his literature reflects the diverse cultural traits of a range of ethnic groups and nationalities. He is regarded as a writer who portrayed the solidarity of the Uzbek human beings by means of depicting their connections and relationships. His works also contributed to schooling via showcasing the development of one of a kind societies. In Berdaq's works, one can look at the vast range of literary techniques, significant content, and expressive abilities. His literature embodies heroic qualities, the transformation of men and women over time and their interactions with society, challenges and rewards, love and contentment, and extremely good non secular and philosophical discussions. Berdaq holds a full-size place in Uzbek literature as he stood out among exceptional eras and ethnic groups, making a great contribution to the improvement of heroic literature. The modernity, spirituality, and creativity of his literature emphasize Berdaq's pioneering qualities, confirming his vicinity and importance in the records of literature.

Berdak is recognized as one of the key figures in Qoraqalpoq literature. Born in the Qoraqalpoq area of Uzbekistan, his identify and literary things to do have played a fundamental function in the area of literature. Berdaq marked a length of development in Qoraqalpoq literature in the 19th and 20th centuries. As a pioneer, he was once actively concerned as an educator, storyteller, and philologist closer to the give up of the 19th century and the opening of the 20th century. His works included valuable historic and factual substances of Qoraqalpoq literature.

Berdak's special features are closely associated to interconnectedness, historical cultural environment, maintenance of the literary environment,

teaching language, and the integration of people education. In his works, the Qoraqalpoq people, their history, climate conditions, herbal landscapes, literary knowledge, and their religious-spiritual lives are prominent themes. His innovative undertaking encompassed the style, language, and historical knowledge of Qoraqalpoq literature, incorporating empirical research.

Berdaq's area and role in literature are recounted as one of the good sized figures in the records of Qoraqalpoq literature. His innovative achievements constitute an vital volume of our literary heritage and contribute to the independent development of Qoraqalpoq literature. Berdaq's literary legacy emphasizes ethics, manners, refinement, and beauty. His poetry reflects country wide and ordinary values, patriotism, and friendship between people's, and the standards of everyday moral conduct. According to the poet's words, some mullahs and clever men appeared to be righteous and simply in front of the people, whilst in reality, they verified their hypocrisy.

Berdaq's literary works closely adhere to the oral traditions of the people. His poetry holds a prominent location in the history of Karakalpak literature due to its lyrical and artistic excellence. Many of his works have been translated into Uzbek and other languages. The 170th anniversary of Berdaq's birth was once broadly celebrated in Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan in 1998. In Nukus, a statue of Berdaq was once erected, and a music drama, theatre, street, and faculty have been named after him. Berdaq is considered the famend poet and authentic representative of the Karakalpak people. Numerous schools, streets, cinemas, and libraries in Karakalpakstan endure his name. Additionally, the State Award of Karakalpakstan was set up in the title of Berdaq. This award is presented for super achievements in the field of literature, art, and craftsmanship.

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